

GENDER INEQUALITY AND HUMAN DEVELOPMENT IN BORNO STATE

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Abstract: The study set out to anatomize the menace of gender inequality and its ripple effect on human development in Borno State. The survey research method was adopted using key informant interview as instrument to elicit information from the respondents. Findings from the analysis of the data gathered have proven that human development is undermined by gender inequality in the aspect of educational development, healthcare service delivery and skill acquisition opportunities in Borno State. Such factors among others that often contribute to gender inequalities include the norms and value systems of the people, unhealthy cultural practices, ignorance, illiteracy and religion. Findings further unveils that human development is not given much priority in Borno State, judging from the fact that the female folk in Borno State are still been marginalized, suppressed and their male counterparts still exercise high position of dominance and control over the females, which has a ripple effect on the pace of human development in the Borno State. The study therefore recommends advocating for the domestication of the National Gender Policy 2006, identify possible causes of the continuous resistance from accepting gender equality similarly, gender mainstreaming should be adopted in all policy makers programming. Finally, Government should pay more attention to educational policies that enhance more female enrolment, participation in educational institutions and literacy to enhance women contribution to the growth and transformation in Nigeria.

Keywords: Gender inequality, Human Development, Borno state.

1. INTRODUCTION

Developmental efforts keep stirring the attainment of gender equality from local and international standpoint which includes, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) adopted by the United Nations in 2015 also focused to enhance women empowerment across all sectors and to increase women participation in decision making that would enable them to reach the upper echelons of life and positively contribute to human development. Gender related issues have been a global concern for some decades which attracted scholars, academia and other stakeholders expressing concern for consideration. The most popular issue is gender biasness, which in simple term means the gender stratification or making difference a male or a female. According to the United Nations Development Program's Human Development Report (2013), India ranks 132 out of 187 countries on the gender inequality index- lower than Pakistan (123). The report states that all countries in South Asia, with the exception of Afghanistan, were a better place for women than India, with Sri Lanka (75) topping them all. Nigeria ranks 118 of 134 countries in the Gender Equality Index (GEI) (Randriamaro, 2012). Commenting on the fore, it is apparent that no appreciable development can be made either at the local, national or international platform without recognizing girls and women as equal players in the game of life whilst empowering, up-skilling and investing in them for a better world.

Gender inequality in Nigeria is greatly influenced by different cultures and belief systems. In most parts of Northern Nigeria for instance in states such as Kano, Jigawa and Zamfara States, men use cultures and belief systems to subordinate and frequently exercise dominance over the women. As a result, women are mostly subjected to domestic chores in the households. This has over the years been a subject of controversy among public commentators and advocates especially of the female gender in the aspect of education, life expectancy and income which constitutes the nucleus of human

development. Borno state being one of the northeastern states in Nigeria has also discarded the implementation and domestication of any law that affords the female folk the privilege of attaining equal opportunity or status in the society as the male folk. Gender inequality has paved the way for backwardness in terms of meaningful growth and human development to the state. However, researchers have confidence that if effort is geared towards the elimination of gender inequality and negative bias against the female folk, it will strengthen every area of productivity and promote sustainable growth and human development to the society. The importance of feminism has been steadily growing and gaining intellectual legitimacy. Gender Inequality means disparity between men and women in different social, economic & political, cultural and legal aspects. Thus, several national and international organizations are trying to promote the advancement of women and their full participation in developmental process & trying to eliminate all forms of inequality against women. However, forms of gender discrimination still remain unquestionable realities in most parts of the world, particularly in developing countries (United Nations, 2014).

From this viewpoint, eliminating barriers that limit women's capabilities, opportunities and empowerment has been shown to generate a positive feedback loop between women's conditions and human development (Cuberes and Teignier, 2013; Kabeer and Natali, 2013). Moreover, inequality of any sort violates the core principles of human development which include equity, efficiency, participation and empowerment and sustainability (UNDP 2013).

In Borno State, gender inequality still remains one of the prevailing hindrances for human development that can streamline developmental efforts in the state. The females are still been marginalized and suppressed and the males still exercise high position of dominance and control over the females, which has a ripple effect on the pace of human development in the state. Gender inequality is not perpetuated exclusively through differential access to and control over material resources. Women's vulnerability to poor human development is affected by the intersection of their class, gender, and other aspects of their social status (Iyer et al., 2008). From this vantage point, eliminating the drop backs that undermine the capacity, capability, competence, and empowerment of women in Borno State has proven to be a glaring condition that requires empirical investigation. This study therefore intends to introduce a new perspective and fill the gap in knowledge by introducing the aspects of human development to the existing discourse with focus and specific objectives to access to education, healthcare services and skill acquisition opportunities.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

The term "gender" refers to economic, social and cultural attributes and opportunities associated with being male or female (UN-Habitat (2003). In almost all societies, women and men differ in their activities and undertakings, regarding access to and control over resources, and participating in decision-making. Ikechukwu (2013) identified gender as a social institution, cultural construct and power tool. There is a danger to confuse "gender" with "women".

UNICEF (2017) views the concept gender as a social and cultural construct, which distinguishes differences in the attributes of men and women, girls and boys, and accordingly refers to the roles and responsibilities of men and women. Gender-based roles and other attributes, therefore, change over time and vary with different cultural contexts. The concept of gender includes the expectations held about the characteristics, aptitudes and likely behaviours of both women and men (femininity and masculinity). This concept is useful in analysing how commonly shared practices legitimize discrepancies between sexes.

Human development involves equifinality (more than one pathway to a given outcome), a principle of extreme importance, especially when dealing with problem populations (psychological disorders): there is likely not only one way to intervene (or develop the disorder in the first place). International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences, (2001). Human development is defined as the process of enlarging people's freedoms and opportunities and improving their well-being. Human development is about the real freedom ordinary people have to decide who to be, what to do, and how to live. Mahbub ul Haq (1990). Human development is about expanding the richness of human life, rather than simply the richness of the economy in which human beings live.

It is an approach that is focused on people and their opportunities and choices. Human development report (1990). Human development is the process characterized by the variation of material conditions. These conditions influence the possibilities of satisfying needs and desires. They also explore and realize the physical and psychic, biological and cultural, individual and social potentials of each person.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The core of liberal feminist theory is gender inequality. The theory was propounded by Mary Wollstonecraft (1759-1797), through her writings as *A Vindication of the Rights of Woman* commented on society's view of women and encouraged women to use their voices in making decisions separate from decisions previously made for them. Liberal feminism thus calls for equality among men and women since all human beings are created equal. The theorist also calls for the re-patterning of key institutions such as law, work, family, education, politics, etc. to give women equal opportunities with men. Sha (2007) and other liberal feminist scholars are of the view that all people (male or females) are born equal and therefore equal opportunities should be provided for them and that the existing women oppression subordination arose because of the non – recognition and implementation of this principle. The theory contemplates that this marginalization is derived from the pattern of socialization of men and women into different roles in the society.

This according to Sha is further reinforced by discrimination, prejudice and irrationality perpetuated by men, the family and the state and its agencies. To the Liberal Feminists, since women's subordinate position has been institutionalized, and which implies that women cannot as individuals free themselves through change in consciousness, a mass movement is required to organize and coordinate their struggle. Dugbazah (2012) opines that the Liberal feminist theory prescribes to the belief that women can have the freedom to choose their course and an opportunity to achieve their potential within the patriarchal capitalist society.

The liberal feminist theory is quintessential to this work because it provides a clear justification for the understanding of gender inequality because it views all human beings as equal and therefore everyone should be even equal opportunity to pursue their passion in their various field of interest, have access education, resources, opportunities, healthcare services, empowerment programmes, quality of life and other benefits associated with the human civilization without any form of restrictions, reservations or discrimination.

The policy implications of this approach include legal reform, women's political participation, increases in the enrolment of girls in education, and access to meaningful employment opportunities. The perception of this theory is hinged upon inculcating programming that uses robust analysis of the different needs, roles, relationships and experiences of men and women in the assessment, planning and implementation of policies that has direct impact on their lives.

The theory seeks to change power relations that assign women and girls a low social status in an effort to redress debilitating inequality. Liberal feminism is valid to this study because it focuses on the attainment of equality in education, income level, workplace, and political rights. The theories ultimate goal is the achievement of gender equality in the public sphere, which includes but not limited to equal access to education, equal pay, ending job sex segregation and better working condition which in turn will pave the way for human development in a society.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study design is based on qualitative method that generated respondents from estimated population of 5, 860, 183 persons in Borno state according NPC (2016) report. The sample size stands at sixteen (16) persons consisting of head of schools, medical practitioners, in and out patients, skill acquisition beneficiaries, students, senior's cadre staff of the ministry of women affairs and social development. Purposive sampling method was used to arrive at the sample size. However, a criterion was utilized in justifying the reason for the selection known as the inclusive and exclusive criteria as identified by John W. Creswell. Data was collected within the stipulated time and were all interviewed at their various offices' convenient locations. The interview conducted was very brief and lasted for not more than thirty minutes for each of the respondent. Thematic analysis procedure was adopted in the study to analyse the transcripts recorded from the interviewers.

MAIN FINDINGS:

Theme One: Gender Preference and Limitation to Educational Development

Gender preference and its limitation to educational development emerged as a theme because majority of the respondents are of the opinion that gender preference posed a huge limitation to educational development. The existence of gender preference is reality within the educational sector, which the male gender is given more preference at the expense of the female which constitute a major setback for educational development as a whole within the given context.

This reality can be closely related to the historical development of the norms, culture, and believe system of the people that promote exclusion relegation and marginalization of the female folk, constantly contribution to their limited participation in development efforts. Education development serves as one of the major factors that makes for human development in every society within the human civilization because it paves the way for people to eradicate ignorance and carelessness. Educational development is also one of the key indicators for measuring the level of human development within a given society.

Sub-Theme One: Slow Pace of Educational Development

The interview conducted made inquiry to measure how the menace of gender inequality has contributed to the slow pace educational development within the study area. The responses received from two different respondents from the educational sector makes it very glaring that elements of gender inequality exist within the four walls of the educational sector in the study area and further proves that the female gender are mostly the victims of inequality for various reasons as provided by the two respondents.

In the researchers attempt to find out about **Respondent K3's** perspective about the issue of gender inequality and educational development in the education sector, asserted that *"in my view, the concern for gender inequality has been prevalent in the education sector largely because women are still not given more opportunity to actively contribute their own quota in bringing new ideas and alternatives that can positively impact the educational sector and bring about growth and development"*.

As observed from the respondent's views, it paints a very clear picture that despite the fact that awareness is been created about the menace of gender inequality within the education sector, it is still in existence since no remarkable or substantial progress has been recorded to clearly prove that there limited or no inclusion for women in policy formulation and implementation processes that can make do for exponential growth within the education sector, as opposed to the men.

Sub-Theme Two: Perceived Treatment Level Between Male and Female Students

Elements of disparity in the context of how the male students are treated in secondary school as compared to the female students. The findings clearly validate the fact that female students enjoy more preferential treatment from the teachers as opposed to their male counterpart, which was proven to the reality in some context.

As to how the teachers treat the female students compared to the way they treat male students **Respondent K3** asserted that *"the teachers treat both the male and female students the same, but in some cases, the female students enjoy more preferential treatment by the female teachers compared the male teachers"*.

When asked why the female students enjoy more preferential treatment than by the female teachers than the male teachers **Respondent K3** again asserted that *"they some male teachers do that because of the fear of losing their respect which is largely a subset of their cultural upbringing that is mostly conditioned in their mind that men are superior to women and that they should always be submissive to them if they want to be seen as responsible people in the society"*.

While **Respondent K4** in his response asserted that *"the teachers both male and female in their school treat all the student the same irrespective of their gender difference"*. This assertion of **Respondent K3** serves as an evident based response that clarifies that the females are preconditioned by culture and their background to believe that the male are superior to them and also hold a superior position in the society that the females cannot attain.

This I believe is the only reason why some male teachers treat the female students differently than the male students. With these type of programming from a very tender age, the females are likely to grow up with a negative pattern of behaviour that often make them see themselves as second class citizens in the society, posing a major hindrance to their life.

If not exposed to the needed knowledge, exposure, and awareness, this type of programming is likely to constitute a major setback for them when they have the desire to rise to the upper echelons of life in pursuit of their passion, desire and ambition within their various areas of interest in life.

Sub-Theme Three: Teachers Employment Level

From observations by the researcher, gender disparity exists in the education sector, contributing to the limited pace of development in the education sector as compared to other sectors within the study area. This disparity is a subset of several factors like norms, culture, religion, ignorance and the attitude of gender advisors that continue to promote gender inequality and creating detrimental effects to the sector and the said community at large.

The researcher went forward to investigate the extent to which gender inequality has influenced the employment of teachers in secondary schools within the study area, because several observations have shown that gender inequality is quite prevalent within the context of the employment level of teachers in the public education sector. **Respondent K3** asserting that *“the possibility of the existence of gender inequality in respect to the employment of school teachers is a reality within the education sector, though from my observation, the margin between the male and female teachers is not that much, it truly exists because in our school we have more female teachers than male teachers at the moment right now even though the difference is not so much”*.

The respondent clearly affirms that the speculation about the disparity in the employment of secondary school teachers is no more a speculation but a reality, in the sense that more females have higher chances of securing employment opportunities to teach in secondary schools compared their male counterparts.

Respondent K4 also added to the conversion by asserting that *“there is currently a high level of unemployment in the country and because of this issue more people are now desiring to be employed by the government to teach in government schools even though some of them do not necessarily have the passion to teach and educate the pupils, but because they don't have any option they seek to become teacher. With the ongoing trend in the society right now about the need to help and support women, government on her own part is also trying to create a balance that is why I think the government employ more women to teach than men. Before now, it was not so, but because things have started changing, the government also need to adapt to what is happening around”*.

The two response above is an affirmation that women have greater chances of gaining employment as teachers as a result of the changing trends, influence in government policy and the need to support females because they have been duly deprived of such opportunities in time past. These has created an avenue for the females to likewise support themselves and become more independent. Furthermore, the researcher makes an effort to examine the rationale behind the limited opportunity given to women to assume leadership positions within the education sector.

Sub-Theme Four: Opportunities in Leadership Positions

As has been observed for decades, women have not been given leadership positions in the education sector particularly when it comes to assuming leadership responsibilities to serve as secondary school principals in the government schools, though there are few exceptions which are the female dominated schools or otherwise known as all-girls school, but apart from them, females are not been given opportunity to become principals in mixed government secondary schools.

In her response, **Respondent K3** asserted that *“for all female dominated schools, only females are allowed to be the principals and so also in the male dominated schools, that I believe is the only opportunity accorded for a female to become principal only in a female dominated school. But it is a big no in mixed government secondary schools. From my own knowledge, the mixed schools that I know of only have male principals for example Shehu Garbai Secondary School. In my knowledge I have never had a female principal in a mixed school only vice principals which is largely as a result of this gender inequality we are talking about because they feel the females cannot run the schools the male will do better even if the females are more educated and have more experience than the males”*.

From his own perspective, **Respondent K4** asserted that *“a lot has changed in the previous years and the females are beginning to get more and more opportunity to become secondary school principals. A simple example is Mairi Government Day School a female is currently the principal and a male is serving as the vice principal”*.

When asked to identify another mixed secondary school that is currently headed by a female, **Respondent K4** was unable to do so and clarified by asserting that *“right now they may not be plenty, since the opportunity has started to be given to the females, I think more other opportunities will still be given to them to become principals only if they have the necessary qualification to be able to make them become secondary school principals”*.

It is true that the female folk are been marginalized and excluded from opportunities that will enable them built their career and rise to the upper echelons of life within in the educational sector which is a resultant effect of unhealthy cultural practices that relegates the female to mere minor positions, limiting them from being active contributors to the educational sector. Some even feel is a taboo to allow women lead when there are more abled men in the state who can perform far better than the women will do. As a matter of fact, it is even worst when we talk about the other local governments within the state.

Theme Two: Gender Preference and Healthcare Service Delivery

Gender preference and healthcare service delivery surfaced as a theme because the responses gotten from the respondents is in tandem with the idea that gender preference exist within the purview of the healthcare delivery system of the health sector. From observations, it is evident that gender inequality poses a major treat to the overall growth and development of the health care service delivery system in the study area.

Sub Theme One: Consultation Priority in Favor of the Female Gender

Consultancy serves as one of the major avenue where patients gain access to see the healthcare practitioner and express their health challenges for possible solutions. This interview however, suggested that there are minimal bases for discrimination on account of patient's gender, but in most cases, priority is seldom given to female gender because there is a general believe that the male have a high propensity to withstand pain than their female's counterparts.

Respondent K1 asserted that *"I have observed from my experience and observation that doctors often give female patients more attention and consideration during consultation because of their natural inability to cope with pain arising from various health challenges compared to the male gender"*.

The above assertion is proving that the female folk enjoy more ease of access to consultancy services in the healthcare system within the study area on account of the common believe that the female has a very slow coping mechanism to enable them withstand pain and other health challenges.

Respondent K2 with another different opinion asserted that *"I can't really say this or that, but currently where I work everybody is just treated the same, but I have worked in some organizations where they usually give preference to women and children, men not so much because they feel men can handle a lot of things, but they feel that women and children are more vulnerable"*.

On the other hand, it is generally believed that the male has more ability to cope and withstand stress and pain in compared to the female. **Respondent K1** again asserted that *"even during queuing to see a consultant, the males are sometimes asked to give their seat to the females who are in critical health condition and cannot be able to withstand pain while queuing in the line before their turn comes to see the doctor"*.

These however indicates that the female folk are given more preferential treatment during consultation because of the general believe that women are supposed to be treated with a high sense of regard than the men just because the females are presumably seen as a vulnerable group of people within the society.

Sub Theme Two: Preferential Treatment During Service Delivery

Another familiar and common practice that has been also observed within the health sector is the preferential treatment some health practitioners give to women and children than the men because the man are seen to have high ability to endure pain than most women and children, which be implication has promoted inequality to some extend when it comes to the treatment of health patients during service delivery.

As asserted by Respondent k1 "from my years of service in the public health sector, like I mentioned especially tertiary institutions like the State Specialist Hospital, we have different specialties for instance the main clinical department, surgery, pediatrics and gynecology so if you are been referred to any of the departments, the person you have been referred to will strongly determine the level of treatment you receive when seeking for professional treatment, but in most cases, the women are given more attention in some departments".

These by implication suggests that in most cases, women and children enjoy professional medical treatment in the healthcare service delivery system as opposed to the male gender. **Respondent K2** *"on the other hand shared a similar opinion and asserted that "both genders are treated equally because everybody is important, but like I said, anything that has to with women and children more attention is given to them, not that we discriminate, but a lot of times we prioritize women and children"*.

Sub Theme Three: Access to Medical Services

Furthermore, observation have showed that there is gender disparity in the context of having easy access to the available services provided by the government to the members of the general public. In this regard, Respondent K1 and Respondent K2 shared different response to this particular subject judging from their own different experience and observations.

Respondent K1 affirmed by asserting that *“yes there is special treatment for women and children for instance, there what we call free medical treatment for women because that’s what the government has established especially in O&G, you treat them freely which is called (free maternal treatment). Initially it went into dormancy, but the present administration has reverted it back to life, there is even a special budget for that and patients are already accessing it that’s the female patients”*.

And when Respondent K1 was asked if there was any plan by the government to also design a special package for the male folk so that they can also benefit from the free medical services provided by the government the general public, **Respondent K1** asserted that *“in my own opinion it’s desirable, but in my own opinion it may not sustainable so that is why the government is concentrating on the women because you know the female gender are more disadvantaged than the male and they have more medical conditions than the male”*. The response was another affirmation that the female gender seems to benefit more from access to free medical services provided by the government to the general public.

Respondent K2 who shared a different view about these particular question asserted that *“men do benefit more from access to free available medical services provided by the government, women not so much, I worked with the federal ministry of Health, on an intervention programme that they did here in the state called (Health and Emergency Response Project) and one of the reasons why the project came into existence was because of the insurgency and they noticed that a lot of women and children are not on the receiving end, so they are the ones that cannot easily access medical services, the men can take care of themselves, but the women may not”*.

From observations and discovery, it is very glaring that in some context where a woman is probably the fourth wife in a home which is very common, the man would not really care or she may be one of the wives in a home with plenty children, so when one of the children is sick the man may not really want to permit her to access the medical services because of his cultural beliefs that often pose a hindrance to women having access to medical services.

The goal of several intervention programmes were purposely designed to be a free programme where free medical services, free drugs, free medical tests, were provided of so that people the vulnerable population can take advantage of such free medical services.

Theme Three: Gender Considerations in Skill Acquisition Opportunities

Skill acquisition plays a pivotal role in human capital development because it provides the opportunity for people to obtain skills and knowledge that will enable them to be productive, add value to their society through problem solving ability and help them to overcome the obstacle of life. Skill acquisition is therefore one of the major indices for measuring the human development within a given society.

This research investigated the availability of skill acquisition opportunities within the study area and how gender inequality has negatively imparted skill acquisition opportunities.

Sub Theme One: Opportunities for empowerment

The researcher conducted two Key Informant Interview to investigate the extent to which gender inequality has affected skill acquisition opportunities which has a direct impact on human development. **Respondent 5** asserted that *“the beneficiaries are mostly women because they are placed at a disadvantage position in the society that is why our focus is majorly on them so that they can also have a sense of belonging”*.

The female folk are largely marginalized within the society because they are seen as the minority group in the society that is primarily the rationale behind why they enjoy more privileges when it comes to the issue of skill acquisition and empowerment programmes. The female folk benefit more from skill acquisition opportunities by the government and non-governmental actors because it is perceived that the females generally seldom benefit access to career development opportunities especially within the context of the study area.

However, **Respondent K6** also shared similar view by asserting that *“women tend to benefit more from our skill empowerment programmes simply because they have low propensity to get high earning jobs, to the extent that some even believe that when women are given high position in a high paying job, they usually become arrogant and very disrespectful to the men. A lot of men have complained in time past that when their spouse gets a high earning job, they become very arrogant simply because they earn more money than their husband”*.

One of the factors that enables women benefit from skill acquisition opportunities is because women are placed in a disadvantaged position in the society, from another perspective, it believed that more focused is been placed on women when during empowerment programmes because their chances of securing a lucrative job is low compared to men because there is a general believe which stems from orientation that women become rebellious to their husbands if they earn more income than the men.

Sub Theme Two: Graduation level

Within the purview of measuring the percentage of females that having more opportunity of graduation from skill the available skill acquisition centre in the study area compared to male,

Respondent 5 began with the assertion that *“here in our centre, we have different skills for people to learn and immediately after enrolment, the stipulated during for training them is three months then graduation and particularly for the women, if they do not learn the skill within that three months, we give them additional time to learn before they are graduated. But in the case of the men, I cannot say the same in for them, because most of the women we train are mostly house wives, widows and the vulnerable in the society that is the reason why extra care is even to them to learn the skills so that after their graduation they can make more meaning out of their lives to the extent that some of the married women even begin take care of their entire families when they start making their own income as it has been said (when you train a woman you train a society)”*.

While **Respondent 6** also responded by making the assertion *“that everyone has equal chance of graduation from the skill empowerment programmes irrespective of gender difference whether male or female because the timeframe set for the particular empowerment training is the major determinant of the graduation of the participants, based on my knowledge this is what I know to be in existence”*. It is quite pertinent to note from the responses gotten from respondent K5 and respondent K6 that even though gender difference may quite influence the graduation of participants from skill acquisition centers depending on the purpose, objective of the empowerment programme and the major determining factor that set the pace for when participants graduate is the timeframe that has been set for the completion of the programme.

Sub Theme Three: Societal Acceptance After Graduation

Another very important question is to measure the rate at which males and females gain acceptance within the society after the successful completion of their training from the centers. There has been divergent views and opinions that has been shared as to who gain more acceptance from the society after the completion of their training from the empowerment programme, while some say it's largely the men, others object and say it's the females. **Respondent K5** her observation by asserting that *“you can't even compare because women gain more acceptance from the society after graduation than the men do which stems from the idea that since they are not involved in any negative behavior like prostitution and other social vices, but they decide to use their skills and abilities to lead a decent life, the society should support them in the best way it can to patronize their products”*.

Respondent K6 from her own wealth of experience asserted that *“sincerely speaking, most of the time the only set of skills that enable women enable women to gain more acceptance from the society after graduation are the common skills we all know about like tailoring, bit making, catering and sewing. When in this day and age we talk about improved skills like computer programming, website development, digital marketing and artificial intelligence which women who have passion for it learn the skills but often don't get patronage from the society especially in our own context partly because women in this part of the world are only relegated to everyday skills women are known for like the ones I mentioned earlier. “It will be very for you to see a girl pursuing a career in the tech industry in Borno State that has receive major support and backing from the community, but we also have to take into consideration that the world is fast changing and we also need to catch up with what is going on around the world so that we won't be left behind”*. Support from the community doesn't mean compromising exiting values and believe systems and completely adapting the western culture, but the focus is hinged upon to exploring some of their advanced skills that will also enable us fast track our own pace of development especially in the northern part of the country. And the only for this our backwardness is because some of our cultural practices that we still tend to uphold even with the current changes experienced in other parts of the world.

4. DISCUSSIONS OF FINDING

The major findings are based on responses from investigation obtained from fundamental questions sought from popular opinions of respondents from three (3) critical sectors selected from the study: Health sector, Education sector, and Ministry of Women Empowerment and Social Development. From the popular opinions of respondents, it is evident to note that the menace of gender inequality has impeded the pace of growth and human development in Maiduguri Metropolis. The study further reveals that it is no doubt that gender inequality has eaten deep into the inner fabrics of communities within Maiduguri Metropolis tremendously contributing to the limited provision and access given to women productive and advanced skill empowerment opportunities. This corroborates with the findings of Egbulonu and etal (2018) who also observed that bear the brunt of unpaid work – primarily domestic and care work.

Women have different needs and face greater constraints than men when running a business. Particularly, in developing countries, the limited provision of welfare services, such as lack of childcare and healthcare infrastructures, increases the time women need to spend in the care economy. Low levels of access to efficient resources, technologies and operating practices exclude women, girls, men and boys from fully participating in economic growth and sustainable development.

In addition, the study further reveals that, the system of patriarchy which has long been in existence and been uphold as a value system has in no small way added to the factors that serves as a major hindrance to the education of women. These finding authenticate the findings of Makama, Godiya Allanana (2013) which reveals the Nigerian society is patriarchal in nature which is a major feature of a traditional society.

It is a structure of a set of social relations with material base which enables men to dominate women. Women are therefore discriminated upon from, in most cases, acquiring formal education, mistreated and perpetually kept as house help; the average Nigerian woman is seen as an available object for prostitution, forced marriage, street hawking, instrument of wide-range trafficking and a misfit in the society.

Education is said to be a vehicle that break the shackles of poverty thereby leading to transformation, development and progress. The ability of women and girls to empower themselves economically and socially by going to school, or by engaging in productive and civic activities is still being constrained by their responsibility for everyday tasks in the household division of labour.

The finding also proves that educational facilities are generally believed to be inadequate, and access, limited for many, especially girls and women. Nigeria been classified as a low development country in respect of equality in educational accessibility. Consequently, the study further affirms that women are fewer than men in certain socio-economic activities. As further revealed by the study, the percentages of female folks in leadership positions in secondary schools and the education sector at large is fewer than that of men. The findings also validate the fact that gender inequality a pose threat in access to health-related services and using healthcare services and basic available health resources for the prevention and treatment of diseases. During critical examination of the mortality rates of basic diseases between men and women, it has been seen that gender inequality has a ripple effect on both sexes. However, the studies have shown that life quality of women is more negative than that of men.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The gender is inequality severely undermined human development in Borno state which not unconnected with the socio-cultural practices and believe system among people that translate into the educational, health and skill acquisition activities of the female fork. more gender sensitive approach is pivotal to enhance and accelerate the pace of human development in any given society. Despite growing awareness of the importance for more gender inclusivity and the need to empower women through measures to achieve social, intellectual, and economic equity as a major headway to attain human development, there is still much that needs to be done as an effort to integrate women in the economic activities, educational attainment, and their overall health and wellbeing in the society. Identity possible causes of the continuous resistance from accepting gender equality as the new norm and embracing it as a value system. The government, private sector, and non-governmental organizations should adopt a more gender inclusive strategy that in the process of policy formulation and implementation. Gender mainstreaming should be adopted in all policy makers programming. Introduction of a cultural change strategy that eliminates all forms of unhealthy cultural practices and works for both men and women allowing each to reach their full potential without any form of discrimination. Government should pay more attention to educational policies that enhance female more enrolment, participation in educational institutions and literacy to enhance women contribution to the growth and transformation in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- [1] Afolabi (2003) in Agbalajobi, Damilola Taje (2010); Women's and prospects. African Journal of Political Science and participation and the political process in Nigeria. Problems International Relations. Vol. -4 (2).
- [2] Akın A. (2007). Toplumsal Cinsiyet Ayrımcılığı (Gender) ve Sağlık, Toplum Alita Joseph, The Guardian, Saturday January 22, 2011, page 25
- [3] Alkire, S. (2005b). Why the capability approach? Journal of Human Development, 6(1), 115-133.
- [4] Ankara, s.231-249. Ankara.
- [5] B. Gender, livelihoods and migration in Africa J Dughazah- 2012-books.google.com.
- [6] B. Mary Wollstonecraft and the feminist imagination B Taylor-2003 books.google.com > Cuberes and Teignier, 2013
- [7] Barro, Robert J. and Lee, Jong-Wha (2001), International Data on Educational Attainment Updates and Implications, Oxford Economic Papers, Vol. 3, p. 541-563.
- [8] Cinsiyet, Sağlık ve Kadın kitabı içinde (Ed. Akın A), Hacettepe Üniversitesi Kadın
- [9] D. Cuberes, M. Teignier Gender inequality and economic growth: A critical review J. Int. Dev., 26 (2) (2013), pp. 260-276. Department of Economics, University of Sydney.
- [10] Egruwube, J. (2016) Challenges facing women empowerment in contemporary Nigeria Gender Hub: Sharing knowledge for gender justice in Nigeria
- [11] European Commission (2004) https://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/sites/devco/files/toolkit-mainstreaming-gender-section-1-part-1_en.pdf
- [12] Federal Government (2012), "Statistics on Gender Employment in Nigeria," Abuja: National Bureau of Statistics.
- [13] Federal Ministry of Finance (2012), "National Capacity Assessment Report of Nigeria," Abuja: Federal Ministry of Finance.
- [14] Gaub, O. (2004), an introduction to political theory Delhi Macmillan, India.
- [15] Gender Situation Assessment and Analysis (GSAA) 2006. National Bureau of Statistic 2004.
- [16] Green, B.O (2006). International journal of social and policy issues vol. 4, No 1&2. The development universal consortia, Nigeria.
- [17] Hekimliği Bülteni. 26(2), 1-9.
- [18] <http://www.elsevier.com/locate/jenvman><https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.111809> Citations in page numbers 4 and 21 <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-environmental-management>.
- [19] <http://article.sapub.org/10.5923.j.economics.20140401.07.html>
- [20] <http://hdr.undp.org/en/humandev>
- [21] <http://www.genderhub.org/get-in-the-know/resource-library/challenges-facing-women-empowerment-in-contemporary-nigeria/>
- [22] <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/wmopen-lifespandevelopment/chapter/human-development/>
- [23] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Maiduguri#Economy>
- [24] <https://measureofamerica.org/human-development/#:~:text=Human%20development%20is%20defined%20as,by%20economist%20Mahub%20ul%20Haq.>
- [25] <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/23099>
- [26] <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/31421>
- [27] <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/medicine-and-dentistry/human-development>.

- [28] <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/social-sciences/human-development>
- [29] <https://www.unicef.org/gender/training/content/resources/Glossary.pdf>.
- [30] Ikechukwu, O. N. (2013), "Social Welfare Analysis of Gender Inequality in Education and Employment: Printwell Press Ltd.
- [31] Iloegbunam, N.E. (2006). Rights of women as panacea for repositioning women education in Nigeria. Multidisciplinary Journal of Research Development, 7,(3).
- [32] Iyer, Vijayan Gurumurthy, et al. "Environmental Health Effects of Chromium. A Modeling Approach to Find Environmental Impacts", WSEAS Transactions on Environment and Development (ISSN: 1790-5079), Volume 2, Issue 3. March 2006, pp. 188-197.
- [33] Jump up to: *a b c* Wood, Julia. Gendered Lives. 6th. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth/Thomson Learning, 2005.
- [34] K.E. Ukhurebar, et.al. (RG Journal impact 0.24). <http://wseas.org/> The paper has been cited (Kingsley.et.al) entitled "Effect of hexavalent chromium on the environment and removal technique" - A review ". Published by Elsevier Science Direct in Journal of Environmental Management (ISSN: 0301-4797),
- [35] Kabeer, L. Natali Gender equality and economic growth: Is there a win-win? (IDS Working Paper - No 417 ed.) Institute of Development Studies, Brighton, UK (2013)
- [36] KG Egbulonu, HC Dim, UP Agba - International Journal of.... 2018- indianjournals.com Kabeer and Natali, 2013 N.
- [37] Lagerlöf, N. 1999. 'Gender Inequality, Fertility, and Growth'. Mimeographed.
- [38] Nigerian Census & Gender Population, www.nigerianpolity.blogspot.com/2007/01
- [39] Olowa, O., and Adeoti, A., (2014) Effect of Education Status of Women on Their Labour Market Participation in Rural Nigeria American Journal of Economics 2014, 4(1): 72-81 DOI: 10.5923/j.economics.20140401.07
- [40] Patriarchy and gender inequality in Nigeria: The way forward GA Makama- European scientific journal, 2013 - academia.edu
- [41] Sağlıkına ilişkin Türkiye’de Toplumsal Hizmetlerden Faydalanmasına Etkisi,
- [42] Şahiner, G. (2007). Toplumsal Cinsiyet ve Kadına Karşı Şiddetin Kadınların Üreme
- [43] SK Chynoweth, J Freccero... Reproductive health... 2017 - Taylor & Francis.
- [44] Soetan, R. (2003)" An Evaluation of Governments Poverty Alleviation Programme: The Way Forward", being paper presented at Dialogue on Governments Poverty Alleviation Programme, Center for Gender and Social Policy Studies, Thailand.
- [45] Sorunları Araştırma ve Uygulama Merkezi, Hacettepe Üniversitesi Yayınları,
- [46] Streeten, Paul (May 1994). "Human Development: Means and Ends". Human Development. 84 (2): 232–37.
- [47] Subaşı, N. Akın, A. (2003). Kadına Yönelik Şiddet; Nedenleri ve Sonuçları. Toplumsal
- [48] The legacy of human development: a tribute to Mahbub ul Haq OA Snchez- 2000- Taylor & Francis
- [49] Understanding Issues of Empowerment, Gender and Poverty Alleviation Strategies In Nigeria Adole Raphael Audu 2018 Pg.41-42
- [50] UNDP (200 _____(2003b), Millennium Development Goals, Source: <http://www.undp.org/gender/docs/mdgs/genderlens>.
- [51] UNDP (United Nations Development Programme). 2013. Human Development Report 2013: The Rise of the South: Human Progress in a Diverse World. New York
- [52] UN-Habitat (2003) (2005), A Conceptual Guide to "Gender"www.unchcs.org And <http://www.unhabitat.org/gov>
- [53] UN-Habitat (2003). Global Report on Human Settlements: The Challenge of Slums. Nairobi: UN-Habitat.

- [54] United Nations Development Programme (1997). Human Development Report 1997. Human Development Report. p. 15. ISBN 978-0-19-511996-1.
- [55] United Nations Development Programme (2012), "Human Development Report," New York: Palgrave Macmillan. pdf3a), Human Development Report 2003, Oxford University Press.
- [56] United Nations, The 2030 Agenda and the Sustainable Development Goals: An opportunity for Latin America and the Caribbean (LC/G. 2681-P/Rev.
- [57] Wood, Julia. Gendered Lives. 6th. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth/Thomson Learning, 2005.
- [58] World Bank Group (2019) Profiting from Parity: Unlocking the Potential of Women's Business in Africa.
- [59] World Bank/IBRD/IFC (November 2018) Nigeria Systematic Country Diagnostic (SCD) Transitioning to a Middle-Class Society
- [60] Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Gülhane Askeri Tıp Akademisi Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü,